

Transmission Problem Of Tax Wedge And GDP In Export Variability In Turkey And Effect Of Foreign Trade Balances

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Abstract

This study aims to analyse a structure in which the tax wedge affecting exports and the impact scales on foreign trade balances are questioned together with the increase in national income, in a process where export values in Turkey have recently deviated from the target points. This analysis framework is also aimed to reveal to what extent the positive correlation of export variability in Turkey with the increase in national income has been also affected by a process that has also resulted periodically in significant current account deficits in foreign trade balances. In this regard, calculating and analysing target deviations for the analysis of export variability in Turkey periodically, determining the periodic impact level of export positions in foreign trade balances, as well as knowing their mutual relations with the variability of consumer goods within the country, have made it inevitable for directing the sectors. This study also brings up the discussion that the blocking of the variability in consumption levels with high price increases, as well as the shrinkage effect in national income, which causes a significant disruption in reaching the target export positions in the recent increase in export-oriented investments in Turkey.

Keywords: Domestic Consumption; Export Variability; Foreign Trade Balances; Gross Domestic Product; Tax Wedge.

1. Introduction

The variability of export increases in Turkey reflects a meaningful relationship with some macroeconomic trends that have emerged due to this phenomenon, especially in recent years. The changes in foreign trade balances that affect export variability in Turkey form a whole with the impact value of Gross Domestic Product and consumer goods on national income and its relationship with export revenues. While this transformation framework provides an important framework for increasing exports to reach targeted values, it also needs an analytical framework that can be directly associated with different macro variables. Therefore, this situation has made it inevitable to determine some impact values of target export increases, especially in Turkey, which can be expressed in different values. This inevitability is associated with factors that may arise especially with a macroeconomic effective structure, and determines its national structural economic and political position with the impact of domestic production and consumption volume on sectoral regulations. Creating a public policy that aims to create added value, especially this fact means in the production of export-oriented sectors to provide support to export-oriented sectors and to direct the added value created on national income to export-oriented targets. It should also be taken into consideration firstly that the infrastructure of this approach is inevitable and while this approach focuses on export increases expresses a linear effect in which national income variability increases and aims a positive contribution to export increases for Turkey. Although this economic-political approach requires the inclusion of other macro values, especially employment, it emphasizes the importance of an export-oriented growth level approach, especially for Turkey. It also reflects a situation where foreign trade imbalances and negative variability have a negative impact on target export increases in Turkey including tax wedges as related to the tax burden.

Taking this long-term structure under control and ensuring that the targeted export increases become meaningful emphasizes the importance of the existence of a balanced model in which exports abroad are balanced and related to the local consumption process. This reality is based on the existence of an analytical framework that enables target export increases to emerge positively in a country where consumption volume is increasing in Turkey, in the process of increasing export potential with the support of public financing. This reflects the periodic priority approach in Turkey is the accelerating effect of consumption-based sectoral developments and positively affecting foreign trade deficits or imbalances. In a framework where all determinations regarding the focus on the target economic growth standards have been significant for the last period in Turkey, a framework is forward in which effects such as tax wedge with foreign trade balances and their scale of impact. Throughout the research process, it was observed that the effects of these factors on seasonal export variability varied at different scales. In particular, it has been determined that the positive impact of foreign trade balances positively affects current account deficits and contributes significantly to the variability of export increases. The justification for this structural phenomenon is this structure has expressed a meaningful-effect structure as related to the sectors based on sectors that made exports periodically as related to Turkey. In this context, the position of sectoral balances, where domestic periodic consumption balances are included in the process, brings into question also the discussions that are intended to be analysed within the framework of a periodic interaction that may occur with the impact values of target growth.

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2. Literature Review

It is possible to talk about the existence of meaningful studies recently regarding the effects of export variability in Turkey based on national income and foreign trade balances, which can be handled primarily in a tax-oriented framework. However, before moving on to these studies, the study put forward by Rothwell (1963) considered the most fundamental among the studies on global exports and export taxes, where our subject is theoretically emphasized. This study empirically examines the structural relationship between exports and the tax burden on exports, which is considered fundamental globally. It is a meaningful study reviewing the tax burden wedge and the degree of impact of taxes on underdeveloped countries. The study supports the principles and opinions of the approach in our research for Turkey.

It can be said that the most critical study on export variability in Turkey is perhaps the study conducted by Öztürk and Acaravcı (2003). An empirical research study that explicitly investigates the effects of exchange rate variability on Turkish exports can be considered an essential analytical study in which the impact of exchange rate variable values on the increase of exports is questioned with other fiscal-economic macro variables. The findings in the study are meaningful, especially in revealing the relationship between exchange rate variability and the devaluation process in currency values based on foreign trade balances and export variability. On the other hand, another critical study comes from the study conducted by Sönmez (2005), which expresses the macroeconomic dependence of exports in Turkey based on import coverage ratios. This study presents a qualitative approach in which the export-import coverage ratio is evaluated periodically and included in the process as a source study in which the characteristics of the foreign trade balance change process are revealed from the perspective of economic development and export increases. The study of Hall et al, (2010), who structurally and analytically address the export problem at the global level and essentially support our research study, reveals a meaningful contribution to the framework in terms of forming Turkey's export approach dynamics as theoretical. Besides, the findings of the IMF (2022) and Slacalek et al, (2020) studies, which present an economic model based on export increases and address the issue with the tax wedge, foreign trade balances, domestic consumption goods impact values and quality impact values, have revealed a significant theoretical contribution to the process for emerging economies.

Two other critical Turkey-focused studies that analyse export increases analytically are the studies of Taştan (2010) and Takım (2010). In particular, Taştan's study, in which the spectral analysis of the causality relations between export increases in Turkey and economic growth is supported by the research in another study by Takım, reveals significant empirical findings that the Granger Causality Test. This research also shapes the study of the relationship between GDP and exports in Turkey, including tax burden, foreign trade balances and domestic consumption level intended for current-actual researchers. In addition, the findings of the study conducted by Özcan and Özçelebi (2013), in which the validity of the export-led growth hypothesis was questioned in Turkey, and the findings of the analytical studies conducted by Aydın and Sarı (2014), in which the relationship between exports and Gross Domestic Product in Turkey were investigated, are supported by these studies in which the process is still questioned today. In addition, the study by Sağlam and Egeli (2015) discussed the export variability problem more recently, in which the export-led growth hypothesis is

questioned in a Turkey-based studies by Atsan (2017), and Eren and Tüzün (2019), covering the years 1984-2012. These researches are significant in putting forth the determinants of tax capacity and tax effort related to export variabilities and increasing in Turkey. These studies open an essential horizon for current studies in revealing the structural analytical relationship between the financial reasons for this phenomenon and macro components such as foreign trade balances and GDP. The export change-oriented structure of these studies is also supported by the qualitative-structural framework put forward by the study conducted by Rakıcı and Aydoğdu (2017) on evaluating the relations between tax performance and export limits in Turkey after 2000. Yurdakul and Aydın's (2018) and Sezgin and Sezgin's (2020) studies, which focus on Turkey and the relationship between economic growth and foreign trade, are meaningful in that it is one of the studies in which foreign trade balances and export variability. Those studies have been included in the process with current findings. The empirical findings in this study have revealed a macro variability process that is compatible with our results regarding Hazman's (2019) framework, which deals with the relationship between export variability and the basis of current account deficits and GDP as the elements that influence tax performance in Turkey, considering both studies to provide a fiscal perspective on current export policies in Turkey is significant. The study, conducted by Sahin (2019) and presenting a Turkey-focused impact of high technology export in economic growth analysis, aims to support the increase in consumer goods with the technological infrastructure that provides the increase in export consumer goods and is a study that highlights the effectiveness of domestic consumer goods in the process. The studies of Yilmaz and Sensoy (2022), and Tekin et al, (2009), which reveal the scale effect values of the components that indicate a possible negative process of recent export variability, also revealed essential findings. This research found the relationship between economic growth and exports meaningful with current foreign trade balances and reasoned fiscal negative impact scales at the negative level.

3. Periodic Position Of Export Variability In Turkey And Financial-Economic Process Affecting Foreign Balances

The export potential in Turkey exhibits a pronounced degree of periodic variability, particularly in recent times, characterized by diverse magnitudes, thereby shedding light on pivotal historical insights. A discernible dynamic unfolds, where certain developments about the post-1983 era, serving as the foundation of our investigation, exerted a substantial and direct influence on outcomes in the post-2010 period. This structural paradigm, characterized by imports escalating at a rate surpassing the continuous expansion of exports, engendered notably substantial current account deficits. Consequently, this configuration precipitated a fluctuating contractionary impact on import levels concurrent with the recent upsurge in exports, yet intriguingly, the level of the current account deficit exerted a positive influence on export variability (Aydın & Gül, 2020). The structural dynamics at play, which bestow a constructive impetus on the current account deficit through a nuanced scale effect, have assumed an even more favourable disposition with the advent of elevated export values following the year 2020, thereby metamorphosing it into a substantive asset marked by a high export potential. Regrettably, this constructive trend failed to substantially influence imports, particularly in the post-2018 era, within the context of the export-to-import ratio (Özker, 2023). This intricate mechanism, embedded within a framework that lends itself to expression through diverse numerical values, has materialized as a pivotal scale impact metric within the ambit of our investigation. This phenomenon, coinciding with heightened public financial incentives post-2010 and their attendant constructive impact on export-oriented sectors, has engendered a discourse-analysing framework that informs diverse economic development policies, steering the assessment and scrutiny of export values along

different trajectories (Özkan & Civelek 2021). Chart 1, below, offers a concise section segment encapsulating Turkey's recent export variability dynamic:

Source: İthalat İhracat Bilgi Platformu (2023), *Türkiye'nin En Çok İhracat Yaptığı Ürünler Ve Ülkeler 2022 – 2023*, <https://www.ihracat.co/2023/03/turkiye-en-cok-ihrac-edilen-urunler-ve.html> (Accessed September, 29.09.2023).

Graphic 1. Turkey's Recent Export Variability (2013-2023)

As depicted in Chart 1 above, the noteworthy fluctuation authority in Turkey, particularly evident in the post-1980 era, becomes conspicuous with the escalating export variability, particularly after 2010. Within this context, a noteworthy situation emerges wherein, as of December 2022, imports stood at 33.3 billion dollars, surpassing the export level of 22.9 billion dollars. This trend, albeit accompanied by a marginal contraction effect, persists in the current account deficit trajectory, notably accentuated in December, which witnessed the highest import figures over the entirety of the 12 months in 2022. The deviations in export provision limits substantially influenced the current account deficits, thereby exposing the equilibrium position.

The reduced export performance observed over the 12 months of 2022 culminated in recording the highest foreign trade deficit to date, primarily due to the exceptionally elevated import rates employed as a benchmark for Turkey in 2022 and the subsequent years. In January 2023, Turkey's exports amounted to 19.4 billion US dollars, reflecting an increase of 1.85 billion dollars compared to the preceding year. Subsequently, Turkey's exports in February were 18.6 billion dollars, registering a 6.4% decrease. It is imperative to underscore that the compilation of Turkey's export data, especially when scrutinizing the initial two months of 2022 and 2023, demonstrated a cumulative rise of 1.5%, culminating in 38.8 billion dollars. In light of these figures, our analysis facilitates a succinct summarization based on proportional values within the context of evaluating export variability in Turkey, underpinned by historical developments, particularly those of recent time (Tiryaki et al, 2019)

The critical approach for analysing current account deficits, especially during an academic examination of export growth in Turkey, is a current account balance framework that emphasizes the relationship between imports and exports. This framework provides a meaningful way to examine export variability, particularly highlighting the relationship with national income and explaining its impact on current foreign trade account balances (Eryiğit, 2012). This approach adopted in our study also requires

analysing the indirect association of sectors associated with foreign trade balances with local consumption variability. Therefore, each variability value in our study is expressed as a percentage increase in scale effects, and this approach is essential for rationally analysing significance values in our model.

The relationship between current and trade balances in Turkey is considered to account for, especially in a period of high export values in Turkey (Turkish Statistical Institute, 2023). It is impossible to consider domestic demand separately from the effect of national income, and increasing export-oriented investments show that a higher value-added economic process is meaningfully supported. In particular, a balanced profile in which foreign trade balances consist of energy imports and other purchases is seen as a result of increasing export variability in the context of current account balances (Demirer et al, 2020).

In addition, it is observed that the current account deficit and increases in debt resulting from the decrease in foreign exchange reserves directly affected export increases and current account balances in the post-1980 period. The ratio of domestic consumption goods to exports has not decreased, reflecting a period in which Turkey's external dependency is slowly decreasing, and current account deficits are decreasing. This indicates a positive development in which Turkey's dependence on foreign markets has decreased and become less vulnerable to economic shocks (Akçağlayan and Tuzcu, 2023). Although there was an economic contraction throughout the world during the 2001 and 2009 global crises, there was a slight growth in the Gross Domestic Product in Turkey. Chart 2 below shows the variability in the current account balance from two crucial perspectives, particularly in the post-2000 period.

Source: Attila Yeşilada (2022). *Turkey heralds new export record, but trade deficit still \$45.9 bn*, <https://www.paturkey.com/news/turkey-heralds-new-export-record-but-trade-deficit-still-45-9-bn/2022/> (Accessed September, 26.2023).

Graphic 2. Current Account Balances and Variability of Current Deficits Related to Foreign Trade Balances in Turkey

As seen in Chart 2 above, this phenomenon also indicates that the foreign trade balance continues with a negative trend that constantly creates a deficit. The absence of a foreign trade surplus in the

post-1980 period indirectly indicates a period in which the Gross Domestic Product experienced significant deviations. This essential provides a critical framework for understanding the complexity of Turkey's foreign trade and current account balances.

Turkey has experienced variations in its welfare level, where it preferred higher-cost goods in the production of imported goods, and this preference had negative effects on domestic inflation (Çiftci, 2014). In this context, the low ratio of domestic production goods to exports caused current account balances to remain negative for a long time in a period when export growth exceeded imports. Continuing foreign trade imbalances, especially with negative values, have caused the foreign trade deficit to increase and fluctuate.

However, after 2020, there was a significant increase in Gross Domestic Product rates with a structure that supported export-oriented sectors, which revealed a process that had a positive, albeit small, impact on economic growth despite the foreign trade deficit. In this context, it is seen that the situation of the Gross Domestic Product positions, which create a positive impact value with the positive change effects on the current account balances when the current account balances are in question, also constitutes a significant impact scale (Adem & Bengü 2018).

Notwithstanding the seemingly stable trajectory of periodic export variability in Turkey, particularly in the aftermath of the 1980s, the upsurge in imports has translated into the emergence of a formidable current account deficit potential. This impression also reveals that the values discussed within the scope of issues that can be expressed from a different perspective, especially the domestic product, which can also be defined as national income increase values, significantly positively impacted the current account deficits. Its peak positive effect was in 2013. In this context, it is possible to observe the increases in the exchange values of GDP in US billion dollars in the post-1980 period in Turkey in Chart 3 below:

Source: Statista (2023). *Turkey: Gross domestic product (GDP) in current prices from 1987 to 2028*, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/263757/gross-domestic-product-gdp-in-turkey/> (Accessed September, 26.2023).

Graphic 3. Changes in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Values as Economic Growth in Turkey

As seen in Chart 3, in the period after 2023, although the increases in GDP levels positively affected current account deficits, the expected positive effects in terms of current account deficits were not revealed. The positive correlation of GDP on increasing export rates is far from the expected positive values for current account deficits. This situation also has a significant positive impact on current account balances in 2021 and 2022. It is considered an essential cause of short-term fluctuations, especially in imported energy items, as it is more affected by exchange rate-oriented costs. This position remains far from presenting a stable foreign trade balance despite the increasing export rate after 2022.

Foreign trade balances have entered a trend of deviation from the target limits, and an expected positive change in export exchange values has deviated from the impact value, a process in which the positive financial contributions provided by GDP remain weak. Even if there is a meaningful parallelism with GDP on the current account deficit balances with a short-term positive increase after 2021, it is impossible to talk about an absolute positive impact value that this phenomenon is reflected in the foreign trade balances (TCMB, 2023).

It should be emphasized that even if the change values in GDP, especially the scale effects on export limits, reveal a trend compatible with the current account deficit balances, it is challenging to discuss favourable absolute compatibility with the export increase values. Besides, this balance formation that includes GDP and foreign trade and the current account balance analysis of export variables in Turkey in the post-1980 period also reflects a structure particularly affected by domestic consumer preferences. Based on mutual proportional changes in the export and import balance, this approach aims to create a more meaningful analysis model by considering the proportional effects of domestic consumption increases (Straub, 2019).

4. Empirical Model Approach

In determining the periodic export variability in Turkey after 1982, it was aimed to create a meaningful impact scale related to the subject in the Gross Domestic Product GDP variability process in the relevant period. A periodic analysis, in which the variations in foreign trade balances directly associated with the findings in our study included in the creation of the empirical model, was also discussed in a factual framework associated with domestic consumption expenditures. However, a sectoral approach was adopted for the increases in export variability and the effect of the tax burden on labour on a sectoral basis was considered as a tax wedge and included in the model. Time series-based variables such as the percentage change in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) are included in the model as factorial independent variables to represent the economic growth trend in Turkey, in a position that creates a possible structural contrast with the sectoral tax burden.

The primary purpose of using the NARDL - Non-Linear Bounds Testing Approach Data Analysis approach in creating the model within the framework of our study is that the time series subject to the model is not in a linear framework. Ramsey verification test was used to test the reliability of the model in determining the scale effects of independent components, and the reliability of the model and analysis results was tested by determining probability values within the framework of fixed and non-constant trends as a result of stationarity tests, where significance levels were considered at $p < 0.05$ level.

This situation also reveals a process that is included in detailed analyses after ensuring stationarity by differentiating the variability levels of each series. NARDL-Non-Linear Boundary Test Approach Data Analysis was important in determining the significance of the findings and their effects at a larger scale, with the infrastructure it provided for subsequent Threshold analyses. In other words, a data analysis framework the applying based on the application of the "Threshold Limit Test" of the significant standard deviation values and R-square values, and the predictive values were further interpreted using the scale values. The theoretical framework of the NARDL analysis is also discussed in a basic framework of the ARDL model in a theoretical structure expressed as follows:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \beta_2 \hat{Y}_i^2 + \beta_3 \hat{Y}_i^3 + u_i \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$H_0 : \beta_2 = \beta_3 = 0$$

$$H_1 : \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq 0$$

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m \beta_{1k} Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} X_{t-1} \beta_3 ECT_{t-1} + e_t \dots\dots(2)$$

The NARDL, which we took as a basis for the analysis, the variability of the "Export Variability" (*Exp_Vr*), which is the dependent variable, is expressed by considering the dependent variability trend based on negative and positive location as the dependent variable following:

$$x_t^- = \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta x_i^- = \sum_{i=1}^p \min(\Delta x_i, 0)$$

$$x_t^+ = \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta x_i^+ = \sum_{i=1}^p \max(\Delta x_i, 0) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

The conjugate equations for the positive (+) and negative (-) effect values of the "Export Variability" (*Exp_Vr*), which is the dependent variable, can be defined in the following order:

$$Exp_Vr_t^- = \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta Exp_Vr_i^- = \sum_{i=1}^p \min(Exp_Vr_i^0, 0)$$

$$Exp_Vr_t^+ = \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta Exp_Vr_i^+ = \sum_{i=1}^p \max(Exp_Vr_i^0, 0) \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

$$\Delta Exp_Vr_t = \alpha_0 + \delta_0 Exp_Vr_{t-1} + \delta_1 FRN_TRD_BLAN_{t-1} + \delta_2 GDP_{t-1} + \delta_3 TAX_WED_{t-1}$$

$$+ \delta_4 CON_GDS_{t-1} \sum_{i=0}^p \theta_i FRN_TRD_BLAN_{t-1}$$

$$+ \sum_{i=0}^p \lambda_i GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \mu_i TAX_WED_{t-1}$$

$$+ \sum_{i=0}^p \sigma_i CONS_GDS_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{ti} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Table 1. Expressions and Meanings of Model Components in the Model

EXP_VR	Export Variability in Turkey (as annually)
FRN_TRADE_BLAN	Changes in Foreign Trade Values in Turkey (as annual Current Account Balances)
GDP	Percentage Changes in Gross Domestic Product – GDP for Turkey in the Relevant Period (as annually)
TAX_WEDGE	Tax Burden of Employment in the Manufacturing Sector in Turkey as Tax Wedge (as annual)
CONS_GDS	Consumption Percentage variability in Consumer Goods in Turkey according to the base period (as annual)

The fact that the time series that is the subject of the model for our analysis is not in a linear framework is an important reason for choosing to use the NARDL - Non-Linear Bounds Testing Approach Data Analysis approach. In this context, the installation of the non-linear forecast model was first handled with the approach of ARDL - Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bound Test, an autoregressive bound test with distributed lag, in order to test the concept of co-integration. Then analyses were carried out with the Non-Linear Bounds Test Approach Data Analysis - NARDL approach dependent on this series position. In this context, *Estimation Command* has been formatted like below:

$$ARDL(TREND=UCONST)EXP_VR_FRN_TRD_BLAN_GDP_TAX_WEDGE_LABOR_COSTS_CONS_GDS \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Estimation Equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta Exp_Vr_t &= \alpha_0 + \delta_0 Exp_Vr_{t-1} + \delta_1 FRN_TRD_BLAN_{t-1} + \delta_2 GDP_{t-1} + \delta_3 TAX_WED_{t-1} \\ &+ \delta_4 CON_GDS_{t-1} \sum_{i=0}^p \theta_i FRN_TRD_BLAN_{t-1} \\ &+ \sum_{i=0}^p \lambda_i GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \mu_i TAX_WED_{t-1} \\ &+ \sum_{i=0}^p \sigma_i CONS_GDS_{t-1} + \epsilon_{t_i} \end{aligned} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

We can express the estimation model expansion, as an *Estimation Equation*, which will be expressed with the Non-Linear Bounds Test Approach Data Analysis- NARDL- in this framework approach in equation 7 above. Regarding the model can be put forth in terms structurally along with the explanation of the estimation equation in the model below:

$$\begin{aligned} EXP_VR &= + C(1)*EXP_VR (-1) + C(2)*EXP_VR (-2) \\ &+ C(3)*FRN_TRD_BL \\ &+ C(4)*GDP + C(5)*GDP (-1) + C(6)*GDP (-2) + C(7)*GDP (-3) \\ &+ C(8)*TAX_WEDGE + C(9)*TAX_WEDGE (-1) + C(10)*TAX_WEDGE (-2) \\ &+ C(11)*CONS_GDS + C(12)*CONS_GDS (-1) + C(13)*CONS_GDS (-2) \\ &+ C(14) \end{aligned}$$

It was determined that stationarity was achieved with probability values smaller than the 0.05% value obtained after taking the "First Difference" of the time series, the determination of the stationarity of the time series. In this context, first of all, a summary stationarity determination table was created in which all series were considered together and the significance of all series was emphasized together with the 0.05% criterion. Table 2 below presents the summary stationarity table after taking the *First Differences* of all-time series in the model:

Table 2. Unit Root Test Summaries of Group Series

Method	Statistic	Prob.***	Cross-sections	Obs
Series: EXP_VR, FRN_TRD_BLAN, GDP, TAX_WEDGE_LABOR_COSTS, CONS_GDS*				
Sample: 1983 2022**				
Exogenous variables: Individual effects				
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-7.54509	0.0000	5	187
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-11.0834	0.0000	5	187
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	108.046	0.0000	5	187
PP - Fisher Chi-square	131.061	0.0000	5	190

* Automatic selection of maximum lags.

** Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 0 to 1

*** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.

After the summary stationarity table created after taking the First Differences of the series in Table 2 above, the first differences of the unit root test results are again calculated on the basis of the time series *with constant, with constant & trend and without constant & trend* in terms of stationarity.

A time series model was created in which stationarity was ensured with the Augmented Fuller Test - ADF test, in which it was tested in detail. Table 3 below presents these test results:

Table 3-a. Unit Root Test Table (ADF)*

		<u>At Level</u>				
		EXP_VR	FRN_TRD	BLANGDP	TAX WEDGE	LABOR COSTSCONS_GDS
With Constant	t-Statistic	-5.6025	-1.9097	-1.8846	-2.1132	-2.4878
	Prob.	0.0000	0.3246	0.3358	0.2408	0.1272
		***	n0	n0	n0	n0
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-5.5382	-2.2876	-1.7085	-4.5429	-3.5753
	Prob.	0.0003	0.4304	0.7279	0.0043	0.0472
		***	n0	n0	***	**
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-3.5794	-0.5894	-1.8400	0.4300	-0.2859
	Prob.	0.0007	0.4556	0.0632	0.8016	0.5759
		***	n0	*	n0	**

Table 3-b. Unit Root Test Table at First Difference (ADF)*
At First Difference

		d(EXP_VR)	d(FRN BLAN)	TRD d(GDP)	d(TAX WEDGE LABOR COSTS)	d(CONS_GDS)
With Constant	t-Statistic	-8.3927	-5.2788	-4.0185	-9.0676	-2.6204
	Prob.	0.0000	0.0001	0.0035	0.0000	0.0988
		***	***	***	***	*
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-8.2966	-5.3316	-4.0741	-8.9657	-3.6510
	Prob.	0.0000	0.0005	0.0143	0.0000	0.0415
		***	***	**	***	**
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-8.5147	-5.3009	-4.0265	-9.1950	-2.6468
	Prob.	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	0.0097

*Augmented Dickey–Fuller Test

Notes: (*) Significant at the 10%; (**) Significant at the 5%; (***) Significant at the 1%. and (no) Not Significant

Empirical Findings:

For our empirical findings, we first determined the significance values of the equality we created within the framework of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bound Test - ARDL (2, 0, 3, 2, 2) model and the coefficient effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable "EXP_VR". In this context, particularly significant ones were reached in a structure where the R-squared was 0.5647, and the significance of the findings was confirmed with these significance probability values. In Table 4 below, it is possible to monitor the scale and periodic variability effects of the independent variables determined within the scope of the ARDL model on the dependent variable "EXP_VR":

Table 4. The Scale Effects and Substituted Coefficients of the Autoregressive Distributed

Lag Bound Test - ARDL Model

Selected Method and Model: ARDL (2, 0, 3, 2, 2)

Sample (adjusted): 1984 – 2022; Included observations: 37 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 4

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{EXP VR} = & - 0.356454974272 * \text{EXP_VR} (-1) - 0.645705626058 * \text{EXP_VR} (-2) \\
 & + 1.37776670355 * \text{FRN_TRD_BL} \\
 & - 2.30865520284 * \text{GDP} + 0.416329036341 * \text{GDP} (-1) + 2.27265948343 * \text{GDP} (-2) \\
 & + 4.5223362237 * \text{GDP} (-3) \\
 & + 1.64648200184 * \text{TAX_WEDGE} - 6.62689597458 * \text{TAX_WEDGE} (-1) \\
 & - 4.6493508949 * \text{TAX_WEDGE} (-2) \\
 & - 3.18808707342 * \text{CONS_GDS} - 0.104598070046 * \text{CONS_GDS} (-1) \\
 & + 2.16980690186 * \text{CONS_GDS} (-2) + 445.79879904
 \end{aligned}$$

R-squared: 0.564705

F-statistic : 2.295205

Adjusted R-squared : 0.318668

Prob(F-statistic): 0.039485

Schwarz criterion 8.257602

Durbin-Watson stat: 1.99691

As shown in Table 4, the R-square resulting from our ARDL analysis was "0.564," which holds significant importance in our findings. The impact values indicate that an increase in each value of the foreign trade balance positively affects export variability, represented as "+1.377*FRN_TRD_BAL." In terms of GDP, it is evident that a unit value increase in the short term results in a negative effect of "-2.3086GDP" on export variability. However, in the medium and long term, it transforms into a positive position as "+0.4163GDP (-1)," "+2.2726GDP (-2)," and "+4.5223GDP (-3)," directly contributing to positive effects on export variability. On the other hand, concerning tax revenue on labour in Turkey, the direct positive impact of the tax wedge in the short term is "+1.6464TAX_WEDGE" due to fiscal tax anaesthesia. However, "-6.6268TAX_WEDGE" and "-4.6493*TAX_WEDGE" negatively affect the medium and long term. This implies that increases in tax rates, especially on labour income in Turkey, lead to a pronounced negative scale effect, which becomes even more pronounced in the medium and long term. Furthermore, the scale effect of domestic consumption values aligns with the level of negative scale effects experienced by the tax wedge within the context of maximum dependent lag values on export variability, indicated as "-3.1889CONS_GDS", "-0.1045CONS_GDS (-1)", and "+2.1698*CONS_GDS (-2)". Moreover, the analysis carried out in this context, using the method selected model Non-Linear Bounds Test Approach Data Analysis – NARDL (4, 4, 3, 4, 4, 3), holds significant importance in identifying both positive and negative nonlinear effects in transactions. First of all, Chart 4 below, the significance distribution of the CUSUM of Squares chart, which shows the stationarity of the NARDL test and the significance in the determinations, is important:

Graphic 4. CUSUM Trend Distribution Squares Trend on Stationarity and Significance of the NARDL Test

Table 5 below provides an overview of the scale effects on export variability for the Nonlinear Bounds Testing Approach - NARDL Scale Effects and Substituted Coefficients determinations:

Table 5. Nonlinear Bounds Testing Approach - NARDL Scale Effects and Substituted Coefficients

Dependent Variable: EXP_VR				
Method: NARDL Selected Model: NARDL (4, 4, 3, 4, 4, 3)				
Sample (adjusted): 1983 - 2022				
Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): FRN_TRD_BL_POS				
FRN_TRD_BL_NEG TAX_WEDGE NEG TAX_WEDGE POS GDP_POS GDP_NEG CONS_GDS_POS				
CONS_GDS_NEG				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
EXP_VR(-1)	-0.217247	0.079161	-2.744356	0.0287
EXP_VR(-2)	-0.118245	0.127658	-0.926257	0.3851
EXP_VR(-3)	0.474220	0.159908	2.965573	0.0209
EXP_VR(-4)	-0.573953	0.108972	-5.266993	0.0012
FRN_TRD_BL_POS	-0.879018	0.538485	-1.632390	0.0146
FRN_TRD_BL_POS(-1)	-4.175113	0.701696	-5.950032	0.0006
FRN_TRD_BL_POS(-2)	-3.791795	1.002642	-3.781803	0.0069
FRN_TRD_BL_POS(-3)	-6.543476	1.603718	-4.080190	0.0047
FRN_TRD_BL_POS(-4)	-5.966831	1.197414	-4.983099	0.0016
FRN_TRD_BL_NEG	-5.012416	1.017311	-4.927121	0.0017
FRN_TRD_BL_NEG(-1)	-6.047391	1.301883	-4.645111	0.0024
FRN_TRD_BL_NEG(-2)	-0.417858	1.282338	-0.325856	0.0241
FRN_TRD_BL_NEG(-3)	-3.208294	0.751103	-4.271441	0.0037
GDP_POS	4.994810	1.041430	4.796106	0.0020
GDP_POS(-1)	1.754610	1.768514	0.992138	0.3542
GDP_POS(-2)	6.689085	1.578976	4.236343	0.0039
GDP_POS(-3)	-3.571227	1.534643	-2.327074	0.0508
GDP_POS(-4)	4.106496	1.510181	2.719208	0.0298
GDP_NEG	-10.01334	2.124906	-4.712367	0.0022
GDP_NEG(-1)	3.629639	2.170246	3.515564	0.0098
GDP_NEG(-2)	2.872403	1.134236	2.532456	0.0391
GDP_NEG(-3)	1.716272	1.154847	1.486146	0.0808
GDP_NEG(-4)	1.884796	0.833517	2.261257	0.0582
TAX_WEDGE_POS	-1.957t22	0.485945	1.953747	0.0063
TAX_WEDGE_NEG (-1)	-1.649401	1.194659	1.642763	0.0284
TAX_WEDGE_NEG (-2)	-2.749433	1.693839	2.364944	0.0451
TAX_WEDGE_POS (-3)	-1.404703	1.854373	1.953739	0.0037
CONS_GDS	2.652353	0.631430	4.200551	0.0040
CONS_GDS(-1)	4.578886	0.627816	7.293353	0.0002
CONS_GDS(-2)	4.819711	0.918983	5.244613	0.0012
CONS_GDS(-3)	-1.616104	0.562139	-2.874920	0.0238
C	-745.4602	98.58285	-7.561763	0.0001
R-squared	0.648686	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000145	
Adjusted R-squared	0.945045	F- statistic	22.66515	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.343369			

In Table 5, within the framework of the Nonlinear Bounds Testing Approach (NARDL) test, the observation of elevated negative values in the tax wedge phenomenon affirms the substantial adverse deviation effect associated with this variable, which we have identified as the primary determinant of export variability. Expressly, it is noted that TAX_WEDGE_NEG at lag (-1) exhibits a coefficient of -1.6494, TAX_WEDGE_NEG at lag (-2) exhibits a coefficient of -2.7494, and TAX_WEDGE_POS at

lag (-3) exhibits a coefficient of -1.4047. This determination indicates the relatively modest influence of these deviation effects at the third-stage dependent lag, suggesting that the reduced tax burden, mainly arising from wage increases in labour income. Furthermore, this observation underscores that the initial positive perception, characterized by a tax increase on labour without delay in response to the fiscal anaesthesia effect, is embodied in TAX_WEDGE_POS (-1) with a coefficient of -1.9572. Conversely, this analysis also establishes that the lagged impact values on Gross Domestic Product (GDP), as revealed by the NARDL test, exert a notable influence, particularly in a positive direction. Specifically, the coefficient values for GDP_POS at lag (-1) are observed to be "+1.7546", and at lag (-2) are recorded as "+6.6890". As for another independent variable, the values representing foreign trade balances are as follows: FRN_TRD_BL_POS (-1) exhibits a coefficient of "-0.8790", FRN_TRD_BL_POS (-2) shows a coefficient of "-3.7917". FRN_TRD_BL_POS (-3) is associated with a coefficient of "-6.543476". Notably, the negative impact values for FRN_TRD_BL_POS (-3) and FRN_TRD_BL_POS (-4), with respective coefficients of "-6.543476" and "-5.966831", also signify the presence of a relatively modest threshold effect in terms of dependent lagged coefficient values.

This threshold effect situation has been confirmed by the effect values determined as the Threshold Analysis values below, especially regarding the effect level of the independent variables based on the components that make up the model. Chart 4 below shows the trend impact of the Threshold Analysis for the relevant process:

Graphic 4. Threshold Weight Function Distribution Values

As seen in Chart 4 above, the logistics coefficient for the Threshold Weight Function $c = 16.532$ and the response impact weight of 0.28 reveal a scale effect compatible with the determined GDP values, which has a weighted impact on export variability. On the other hand, within the scope of the Threshold Weight Function, the standard deviation in TREND values is 0.228807, and the probability value is 0.0049, confirming the model's positive and negative impact direction values. On the other hand, the Threshold Weight Function makes sense because the significance of the distribution of the

foreign trade balances the impact values of the tax wedge in the base period and the threshold values in the range of 0 - 0.28 as positive and negative impact distribution. The coefficient distribution of the components in the model is meaningful and compatible with the t-statistic values in the context of the equal coefficient $c = 16.532$.

5. Discussion

Periodic export increases in Turkey were examined in the context of research to understand the impact level of important macroeconomic dynamics. This research focuses on a current and vital issue, explicitly emphasizing the impact of the tax wedge, which is a tax approach on labour on exports. Unlike previous studies, this study, instead of focusing only on Gross Domestic Product (GDP), also discussed the positive effects of exports on economic growth, which are an essential balancing element in foreign trade balances.

Study Results, Comments and Comparison with Past Studies:

This study has achieved essential results by addressing the Turkey-specific scale effects of export variability in a more current and meaningful way than the classical approach. This approach allowed an understanding of the impact of export-oriented sectors on domestic consumption goods and exports during the same period. Considering that countries' national income levels affect exports, examining export increases in Turkey depending on differences in economic growth rates has been the focus of the study. It revealed that it is necessary to investigate the impact level of consumer goods on export variability. In a period when controlling macroeconomic values such as inflation is essential, as well as Turkey's efforts to achieve economic growth trends, it has been observed that foreign trade balances directly affect the export variable. In this context, considering exports as a primary macroeconomic variable shows that, in addition to the positive contribution of GDP and domestic consumption goods, it is inevitable to question the negative impact of taxes on employment in export-based sectors. As a result of this approach, he comprehensively discussed the impact of the tax wedge in Turkey on exports. He examined the effect of foreign trade balances on the economy's general health. This approach went beyond classical methods to understand the impact of tax values on exports and considered Turkey's fiscal position as a financial source of employment in export sectors and its efforts to achieve economic growth targets. Analyses regarding economic and fiscal balance approaches in Turkey in the past periods are seen as a significant deficiency in today's analyses in questioning other macro effects due to focusing only on the existence of economic growth-oriented policies. The approaches emphasized in previous studies, in which the fight against inflation and economic growth policies in Turkey were primarily considered as a mutual correlation, continued with a different approach, in which input costs, especially related to employment power, were not considered much and tax-oriented policies remained in the background as one of the cost factors. This deficiency has also turned into a "Twin Deficits" phenomenon, in which the missing macro dynamics are not included in the process, and the process cannot be controlled in terms of current account deficits in studies targeting analysis of export-oriented policies.

Practical and Contextual Implications of Study

It reveals that this phenomenon means a structural process in which export-oriented policies are put on the back burner, especially when there was an inflation-oriented market control mechanism and effective contractionary fiscal policies in previous periods. However, the fact that the frequent global crisis and analyses of periodic export changes in an inflationary structure are directly related to an analysis of foreign trade balances is crucial. In addition, it should also emphasise that the phenomenon

of Twin Deficits that was not included by export analyses in the past is reflected today as a significant cost from the past periods when it was not included in the subject. Analyses regarding the importance of foreign trade balances, which are directly affected by economic growth-oriented issues, and the added value position created by sectoral development, especially in export variables, confirm the current relevance of multi-focused cross-sectional analyses. In this respect, a multi-focused analysis of export variability based on Turkey has included as a perspective in our study the expression of the economic balances abroad and an issue that affects exports with the accelerating effect of domestic consumption goods. This variability has revealed the tax wedge, especially when the tax burden on labour becomes a production deviation that creates significant deviations in balancing income levels with social policies. Therefore, the current importance of questioning the current reason for questioning the export variability in Turkey with a more cumulative structure, not just a matter focused on sectoral development and economic growth, has been emphasized in our findings. In this context, questioning the hypothesis with a more current and comprehensive approach adds striking realism to the evaluation of the past period and the more meaningful interpretation of the deviations in the past period today. These updated analyses provide significant clarity in the interpretation of conceptual approaches in Turkey, where import deficits are constantly on the agenda, and also provide a meaningful infrastructure with the up to date, more comprehensive scale effects, where future export policies will also be subject. This phenomenon is also inevitable to reform the tax policies based on labour taxing multifaceted structural analyses to ensure the desired stable export variability to the future in Turkey.

6. Limitations and Future Research Directions:

The practical applicability of the findings for Turkey stands out by providing an infrastructure in which the dynamic impact factors in revising export policies and the targets for these policies are primarily considered. Bringing the research of periodic export variables specific to Turkey to a more comprehensive level in the following years plays a critical role in bringing these results to a more meaningful level with the current dynamism of periodic variations and the meaningfulness of our recent analyses. In this context, examining the scale effects of each study, especially calculated for Turkey, offers a meaningful approach to creating an up-to-date structural basis for applications. Interpreting the long-term cyclical export variability in Turkey specifically as a single development trend means a positive level of added value resulting from a high-scale effect in interaction with other macro dynamics that create a high impact value. Within the framework of the findings in our analysis, this approach also reveals the factors that should be considered in the economic decision-making process to support exports and reduce current account deficits. Therefore, the study's findings gain meaning in that the impact factors of macro values focus on more specific impact factors rather than a multifaceted conceptual framework, ensuring compatibility in terms of goals and variability and offering significant effectiveness in practical application.

7. CONCLUSION

When it examines the impact level of critical macroeconomic factors affecting periodical export variability in Turkey, it is observed that essential dynamics such as tax burden on the labour employed by the sectors, national income and foreign trade balance play a significant role among these factors. These positive contributions created a positive correlation with the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and made the impact values of foreign trade effects on export variability meaningful. Moreover, these effects were a component of the positive correlation effects of cyclical export variability in the medium

and long term. In this context, it is concluded that foreign trade effects positively affect national income and export variability. Still, the tax burden on the labour employed by the sectors limits these positive effects. In particular, the increase in the tax burden negatively impacts export variability by increasing the cost of export goods in the short and medium term. However, it has been observed that domestic consumption goods positively affect export-oriented sectors and support exports by creating an accelerating effect that encourages the sectors. It has been determined that when the current account deficits in Turkey are high, deviations in exports are caused primarily by foreign trade deficits, and a vicious circle occurs in which the foreign trade balance directly affects the variations in national income. As a result, this study reveals that the relationship between periodic export increases in Turkey and GDP is based on two main effects: the positive effect of foreign trade balances and the long-term positive correlation effect of periodic export variability. Considering these observations, it becomes evident that the deviation impact values related to GDP and foreign trade balances wield a substantial influence, particularly in a negative direction. The occurrence of a threshold effect, wherein deviations in foreign trade equalisers exhibit greater magnitude than those in tax wedges, contributes to a more pronounced adverse impact on export variability. This phenomenon can be attributed to the heightened joint correlation effect between export variability and foreign trade balances compared to other contributing factors. These findings highlight factors that economic policymakers should consider in supporting exports and reducing current account deficits. In this context, re-evaluating tax burden options by focusing on economic growth-oriented policies in Turkey, especially on export-oriented sectors, reveals that creating a policy framework that primarily targets national income increase based on sectorial incentives is necessary. It should not be ignored that export variability in Turkey significantly contributes to reaching a higher positive trend, including domestic consumption, primarily based on the national income effect. This is an indispensable element of sectorial developments intended for export sectors to achieve potential growth targets. Export variability in Turkey creates a more stable trend in a positive correlation process. It positively affects the current account deficit by creating a movement the contribution value of foreign trade balances and domestic production and manufacturing sectors can be measured.

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Annex 1.

Table 1. Positive and Negative effect sizes of Threshold Regression Test and Constraints

Dependent Variable: EXP_INC_
 Method: Smooth Threshold Regression; Sample (adjusted): 1983-2022
 Included observations: 35 after adjustments
 Threshold variable chosen: EXP_INC_(-5)
 Threshold variables considered: EXP_INC (-3) EXP_INC (-4) EXP_INC_(-5) EXP_INC_(-6)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Threshold Variables (linear part)				
FRN_TRD_BL	0.426565	0.802556	0.531508	0.0052
GDP	1.209235	0.807473	1.497553	0.0173
TAX_WEDGE	-0.176053	1.864302	-0.094434	0.0455
TUK_MAL	0.171669	0.892426	0.192362	0.0091
Threshold Variables (nonlinear part)				
FRN_TRD_BL	-2.202472	1.234744	-1.783748	0.0871
GDP	2.544315	1.848257	1.376602	0.0308
TAX_WEDGE	-1.596375	2.661805	-0.599734	0.0543
CONS_GDS	0.760386	1.309524	0.580658	0.0519
@TREND	0.042303	0.228807	0.184887	0.0049
SLOPE	2.511392	4.685137	0.101737	0.0914
THRESHOLD	16.53195	2.830237	5.841191	0.0000
R-squared	0.388472	Durbin-Watson stat		1.151226
Adjusted R-squared	0.133669	Akaike info criterion		7.403529
S.E. of regression	8.646783			

Annex 2.

Graphic 1. Asymmetry Plot Effect Distribution in the NRDLE Analysis and Stationarity View of GDP's Weighed Effects